

Creating Symbology: Bringing digital maps to life with young people

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Summary

The research describes an innovative animation-based process for creating map symbols that offer a very different way for children and young people to engage in mapping and in communicating their feelings and aspirations about public spaces on Anglesey, Wales. Children can initially struggle with conventional map symbology but demonstrate creativity when allowed to design their own symbols, encouraging them to think about what they are mapping, helping them to engage with ideas around geographic representation, and helping them to develop spatial reasoning and understanding of maps. The research also presents some initial findings and discusses future work.

KEYWORDS: digital mapping, symbology, animation, co-creation, children and young people

1. Introduction

This paper presents initial work on map symbology design and mapping with children and young people (C&YP) on the Isle of Anglesey (Ynys Môn), a local authority in north-west Wales. It is part of an AHRC funded project called Public Map (<https://publicmap.org/en>) which aims to develop a public mapping platform (PMP) to map community level green transition behaviour change. The work presented here describes how we have worked with C&YP to map places and spaces that are important to them using symbology sets designed by them. The objective of the research is to co-create a methodology with C&YP that will allow them to explore places and spaces through map symbology design, create maps using this symbology, and in doing so help co-design the PMP to allow them to share these maps more widely. Studies have shown that children can initially struggle with conventional map symbology but demonstrate creativity when allowed to design their own symbols, often creating intuitive, pictorial symbols reflecting familiar objects and environments (Liben & Downs, 1989; Swienton, 2021). Map symbol creation can encourage children to think about what they are mapping, help them engage with ideas around geographic representation, and help develop spatial reasoning and understanding of maps. This will allow us to better understand what imaginative creative digital mapping can tell us about how C&YP think about play, about place, about where they live and how they interact with it. The research was undertaken by teams in Cambridge, Wrexham and Cardiff Universities, in collaboration with Play Disrupt, a small team of creative engagement practitioners working on the project.

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2. Methodology

2.1 Background to workshops and activities

A series of symbology and mapping workshops with C&YP were ran over one year from June 2024 to July 2025. The focus of the research was to map where C&YP play, or hang out, on Anglesey and why these places were important to them. Suggestions for symbols such as calm, adventure, or friends, came from our initial development workshops with C&YP, and were then used to frame the mapping activity in subsequent workshops. The workshops were ran iteratively using an exploratory, emergent co-designed approach to find ways to adapt the symbology and mapping activity to C&YP. By being curious about why some children might not engage with the task, we discovered new ways to run the activity, and to offer different ways in, allowing different participants to contribute in different ways according to their needs and interests. The unknown is a key part of co-design, as is an openness and willingness to adapt to what children bring to each session. We recruited participants from schools but also from outside of traditional school settings. This included Barnardo's Young Leaders to Young Carers, Mencap Môn and additional needs schools, Girl Guides, and youth clubs in different parts of the island. We ensured that we included workshops for C&YP across the neurodiverse spectrum and with learning disabilities. Table 1 summarises the workshop dates, activities and groups. All the workshops were bilingual (Welsh/English). We worked with groups of C&YP repeatedly at different points of the symbology development process and returned to some groups multiple times as they were able to offer deeper reflections and felt more trust in the process. Putting participants in the driving seat formed the basis of a co-created process, and allowing the process to respond to their ideas and behaviours throughout.

Table 1 A summary of the symbology and mapping workshops

Date	Activities	Groups
June 2024	'Beth yw Map? What is a Map?' workshops. Initial testing and workshop development. Using loose parts to map where participants play, and creating physical, non-digital models of symbols for maps.	Barnardos Meddwl Ymlaen Young Leaders. Canolfan Addysg y Bont at Mencap Môn. Llangefni Youth club years 7-9.
August 2024	7th August - Play Day - maps of where children play using loose parts. 12-15th August - a series of Beth yw Map workshops, starting to animate using models made from loose parts - adding sound and movement. Also developing a shorter drop-in version of symbology for a stall at Anglesey Show.	Play Day at Llangefni rugby club - drop-in. Anglesey Show - drop-in sessions at our Symbology stall across two days. Young Carers workshops x 2 (8-12 year olds, and 13-18 year olds) Girl Guides day - 3 workshops run in rotation - Beth yw map, PD paper happenings workshop, and Environment workshop.
Sept 2024	Symbols from the perspective of highlighting current and potential future play provision plus barriers in Pencraig	Pencraig School
Sept 2024	Symbology workshop (in conjunction with relational digital mapping tool Happenings) - using loose parts to map existing play spaces, as well as building future or dream play spaces.	Canolfan Addysg y Bont (second workshop)
March 2025	Symbology 3rd iteration - digital, with gif uploader added into PMP Alpha Version; Inviting participants to make a symbol from a list of themes, drawn from earlier iterations. Themes- calm; nature; adventure; swing - have pins located on the map and children could replace the generic	Barnardo's Meddwl Ymlaen Young Leaders (second workshop) Girl Guides group. (second workshop) Jesse Hughes youth club, Holyhead.

pin with their symbol. This had a genuine effect on participants that we felt at each instance. Every young person said ‘that’s cool’ when they see their icons.

July 2025 Newborough Beach Public Map event. Symbology 4th iteration utilising FlipaClip to make mixed media stop frame animations. Multiple groups of children making animations in 15 minutes per group - streamlined, faster process.

2.2 Creating Symbols and Maps

The initial workshops used ‘loose parts’ relational mapping – a colourful collection of open-ended, moveable objects made from a range of materials, including metal, plastic (eg Lego), wood building blocks, plasticine, and foam (Figure 1) - to represent tangible and intangible features of plays spaces they’d like to map. A key part of the process was for the participant to tell the story of their model or artwork, as this helps to make sense of their ideas about the places they are mapping. Elements were labelled and photographed, using worksheets to record reasons behind the designs and choice of materials.

Figure 1 The ‘loose-parts’ colourful collection of open-ended, moveable objects made from a range of materials

Having established and tested a design process, we built on C&YP interest in symbol movement by adding an element of puppetry and animation. The puppet/animation then became central to the design of the symbols and an accessible method for C&YP to think about mapping places (Figure 2). We tested a variety of apps on phones and tablets that were free and easy to use to digitise and animate their symbols. The apps had to capture the symbol as a png (static) or a short, animated gif and be able to make the background transparent when uploaded onto the map (Figure 3). The process began with photos of physical models, removing the background, and uploading them as symbols onto the map. We explored a range of free background removing apps, before settling on Unscreen as the most effective. To keep file size minimal, we decided to turn model animations into short GIFs lasting less than two seconds. We explored multiple options for creating GIFs such as <https://tinywow.com/video/to-gif> and the 'video to gif' app, as well as software to remove background

and create a GIF in one: <https://onlinegifttools.com/create-transparent-gif>, before finding that the tablets we used (Samsung Galaxy Tab A9+) allowed us to automatically turn videos into GIFs in the Samsung photo gallery without the need for third party software.

Figure 2 Part of the process of animating a symbol for places to play football

Figure 3 Symbol representing ‘nature’ using natural materials from the surrounding area, shown as original photo (left) and as PNG with transparent background (right).

Engaging with young people to design and test the different apps and workflows helped simplify this process. When working on hand-drawn animated symbols, a young person recommended using an app called FlipaClip, and quickly designed an animated gif/symbol of a boat with a red sail to represent the beach (Figure 4). The process and output were impressive, and this became the main way to create digital symbols in the following iterations. We had looked at Pencil2D, which is a free opensource

animation software, but FlipaClip, being purely designed for making animations, had a simple interface making it more intuitive and easier for C&YP to use.

Figure 4 Animated sail boat using FlipaClip to represent the beach

To experiment with the symbol design on a map we used Canva - a basic design tool with a version which is free to use - with a map of Anglesey as a background. Canva has a background remover, so we could pull the gif onto the 'map' and remove the background with a simple drag and click. This adaptation helped us understand, and to experiment with how animated symbols looked like on the map before finalising and uploading them onto the PMP. Audio recording paired with online screencaptures of maps on Canva also allowed C&YP to record short videos of where and why they were placing the symbols onto the map leading into storytelling via the map. The Cardiff GIS tech team collaborated in the symbology and mapping process to co-design and build the symbology upload feature on the PMP using the symbols created in the workshops. This allows C&YP to upload their symbols onto the mapping platform, share them with other people, and use them to map data on the platform (Figure 5). This symbology mapping feature is still in development.

Symbols

Friends All Symbol Groups

Whole words Show symbol titles Show symbol descriptions

Reset

► Symbol Groups

9 Symbols match your search

Figure 5 Symbology upload and selection feature on PMP showing different symbols designed by C&YP for mapping places where they meet ‘Friends’

3. Findings

3.1 Initial Reflections

Participants relished the opportunity to play with craft materials, even when digital activities were on offer. The mixed media symbols, augmenting pictures of loose parts in FlipaClip, felt like some of the most interesting and most connected to place, for example an animated beach made from with the waves coming in and out (Figure 6). When C&YP used symbols on Canva as a more focused activity, all the children recognised the symbols, even the more abstract. It felt something akin to children having their own language. Symbols that looked similar could often represent different things depending on the intention of the child e.g. one little boy animated a football pitch, but this was made to represent ‘calm’, as this is how he felt when he played with his friends. There were some patterns related to gender in symbol creation. ‘Friends’ initially came from girls and in later iterations the theme was only ever followed by girls. Boys commonly made a football symbol (Figure 7). Many of the young people with learning disabilities made models of imaginary places eg shipwrecks, pirate ships, and created more narratives within their symbols from an early stage.

Figure 6 Animation of the sea coming in and out at Newborough Beach on Anglesey, with a crab

Figure 7 A wooden wheel and Lego figure (animated) representing where to play football on Anglesey on the PMP online map, with a zoom-in section

3.2 Animation and storytelling through maps

As the workshops developed, we saw young people increasingly putting themselves or the world around them in the symbols e.g. filming them hugging a friend to represent ‘places of friendship’. The videos created in Canva allowed a diary or journal style use of the map and feeds into the idea of children using this method to place themselves, their lives, their identities on the map (Figure 8). This also made looking over each other’s contributions to the map more exciting as children could pick out what each other, or even classmates in different sessions, had made.

Figure 8 Screen shots of a Canva video with captions of a young person mapping places on Anglesey and explaining what he is mapping and why he has chosen the various symbols

4. Conclusions

This has been a rich co-design process. We now have an innovative animation-based process for creating map symbols that offer a very different way for C&YP to engage in mapping and in communicating about their places. A key learning was to simplify the process as much as possible, zoning in on what was most interesting to young people. Most C&YP wanted to be silly with the activities, but this has real value and opportunities for young people to map places important to them. Young people were generally very familiar with animation as a form, so it's already a good way in to mapping, and is relatively intuitive. Almost all participants had done some mapping and some animation, but never the two disciplines combined. Next steps for the project are to prototype the process with C&YP from different geographical contexts e.g. deprived urban areas, and work along side partners, such as the Child Friendly City team at Cardiff City Council to explore how the methods can be used to inform child friendly planning policies. Also, while our workshops and the overall

process of symbology was designed in a collaborative process with C&YP, the digital uploading process and digital platform itself could go much further in involving C&YP as co-designers.

5. References

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7. Biographies

Scott Orford is a Professor in GIS and spatial analysis at Cardiff University School of Geography and Planning and WISERD. His research focusses on the spatial and statistical modelling of social and economic processes, participatory mapping, and co-production of data and mapping dashboards

Malcolm Hamilton is creative director of Play Disrupt, a creative engagement studio that works with local authorities, NGO's and universities to expand participation in built environment, health and academia. His research interests centre around play centred methodologies as catalysts for increasing participation in civic and other decision making.

Nia Evans is a creative engagement producer at Play Disrupt and artist working in movement and film. She is interested in how arts-based facilitation approaches can help communities document changes in their area.

Jeffrey Morgan is a software developer at WISERD specialising in interactive data visualisation and GIS and mapping web applications

Andrew Price is a Senior Research Assistant at WISERD and conducts research in the areas of spatial accessibility, open-source GIS software development and geospatial analysis